

Threshold Dynamics of Silver Filament Formation and Rupture in Ag/SiO₂/Au Memristors

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Abstract

Memristive devices with tunable volatility represent a promising platform for neuromorphic computing and adaptive electronics, enabling temporal information processing and gradual memory consolidation. Understanding the threshold dynamics governing conductive filament formation and rupture is critical for precise control of resistive switching behavior. Here, we systematically investigate Ag/SiO₂/Au memristor devices to elucidate the physics of silver filament evolution, revealing the asymmetric interplay between drift-dominated formation and diffusion-dominated rupture processes. Quantitative analysis of filament formation dynamics yields an activation energy of 0.77 ± 0.12 eV for ion migration with field enhancement factor $\beta = 0.21$, demonstrating field-assisted thermally activated silver filament formation. Our experiments confirm that formation and rupture share a similar intrinsic energy landscape but operate under different driving forces: field-accelerated drift versus thermally-driven diffusion. Interestingly, detailed filament dynamics analysis reveals the existence of a critical metastable regime during both formation and rupture processes, where drift and diffusion forces balance, and conduction occurs via trap-assisted tunneling through nanoscale silver clusters. This metastable state exists at specific voltages where drift and diffusion forces achieve dynamic equilibrium, leading to intermediate conductance states between the stable low and high resistance states. Beyond this regime, the system exhibits deterministic behavior: at higher voltages, filament growth proceeds through sequential conduction regimes where Joule heating drives morphological changes in silver nanoclusters that concentrate the electric field and accelerate complete filament formation. At lower voltages, diffusion dominates and drives complete rupture of filaments back to nanoclusters. This enables voltage-tunable operation from stochastic to deterministic modes. Combined with quantitative activation energies and the drift-diffusion framework, our work provides fundamental insight into threshold switching physics and establishes design principles for engineering devices with controlled probabilistic or deterministic behavior for neuromorphic and stochastic computing applications.

Keywords

Memristors, Resistive Switching, Volatile Memories, Memory devices, Neuromorphic computing

Introduction

Neuromorphic computing, which mimics the parallel and adaptive information processing of biological neural systems, has emerged as a promising paradigm to overcome the fundamental limitations of conventional von Neumann computing architectures, where the physical separation between memory and processing units creates severe bottlenecks in energy efficiency and computational speed.¹⁻⁴ Central to this approach is the

development of hardware primitives that can emulate the rich temporal dynamics and plasticity of biological synapses while maintaining energy efficiency.^{5,6}

Memristors serve as two-terminal energy-efficient devices that can modulate resistance through applied electrical stimuli, offering a direct hardware implementation of synaptic weights. Memristive devices are broadly classified into non-volatile and volatile categories based on their retention characteristics. Non-volatile memristors retain their resistance states indefinitely after programming, making them suitable for long-term memory applications and implementing synaptic weights in artificial neural networks. Volatile memristors on the other hand, spontaneously relax to their initial state after stimulus removal. Volatile switches can therefore be used to mimic biological synapses in exhibiting rich temporal dynamics through short-term plasticity mechanisms which are crucial for temporal information processing, coincidence detection, and sensory adaptation.^{7,8}

We built an Ag/SiO₂/Au memristor device as depicted in Fig. 1(a). In these devices, the electrochemically active electrode (Ag in our device) injects metal ions into an insulating matrix under applied bias, forming conductive filaments (CF) that bridge the electrodes (see Fig. 1(c)). The lifetime of the CF dictates the volatility of the device. In the case of NVM devices, the CF is thick and stable with lifetime of several years or decades, while in volatile memristors, the CF disintegrates within micro to milliseconds. Such a small lifetime in volatile devices is a consequence of atomic clustering of the CF to minimize the CF-dielectric interfacial energy.⁹ Such volatile memristors have emerged as promising candidates for diverse applications including neuromorphic computing, in-memory computing, and adaptive sensors.

Despite extensive experimental and theoretical investigations of filament-based memristors, several fundamental aspects of their switching physics remain incompletely understood. While in-situ transmission electron microscopy has provided direct visualization of filament formation and dissolution,^{10,11} the quantitative relationships between applied voltage, switching time, and activation energies have been less systematically characterized. The threshold dynamics governing the transition from high-resistance to low-resistance states—including the role of field enhancement, thermal activation, and the interplay between drift and diffusion processes are critical for predictive device modeling and application-specific optimization.^{12–18} Furthermore, most studies have focused either on formation mechanisms or on rupture dynamics in isolation, with limited comparative analysis of how these complementary processes relate to each other through shared energy landscapes and distinct driving forces. In this work, we present a comprehensive experimental investigation of Ag/SiO₂/Au memristor to understand the CF formation and rupture mechanism at their threshold. We show several stages of filament formation and rupture including the existence of metastable states that occur when a dynamic equilibrium between the drift and diffusion forces takes place.

Results

Filament formation dynamics

Resistive switching in Ag/SiO₂/Au based memristors occurs due to formation of silver (Ag) filament across the two electrodes through the dielectric medium as has been demonstrated in many research articles.^{19,20} The formation of filament takes four major steps: (i) Oxidation of Ag to Ag⁺ ions, (ii) migration of Ag⁺ ions into the dielectric, (iii) reduction of Ag⁺ ions back to Ag, and (iv) nucleation of Ag particles to form a filament. It has been shown that formation and growth of filament depends on the ion mobility within a dielectric and rate of redox reaction of metallic ion within a dielectric.²¹ Understanding the dynamics of resistive switching is crucial for several applications like neuromorphic, reservoir and stochastic computing.^{22–25} The dimensions of our device are given in Fig. 1(a). The volatility of the device can be controlled by adjusting the compliance current of the device. At low current of 0.5 μA , the device shows a volatile memory characteristic as has been demonstrated in Fig. 1(b). When a positive potential difference is applied across the two electrodes (Au is grounded), the device initially shows a very high resistance (order of Gigaohms) or **HRS**. But once the potential difference reaches a certain threshold, V_{set} , a sudden decrease in resistance is observed known as low resistance state or **LRS**, and the device reaches the compliance current (maximum allowed current). However, when we start reducing the potential difference between the electrodes, the device maintains its LRS up to voltages above a threshold voltage, V_{reset} , below this voltage the device returns to its HRS. Both V_{set} and V_{reset} are shown in the graph. The behaviour is known as volatile because the device returns to its initial state (HRS) in the absence of applied potential (Electric Field). To study

Figure 1: **Volatile Memristor Memory Device:** (a) Shows the microscope image of our testing device (Top view). Gold (Au) is the bottom electrode, SiO₂ is the active material and top electrode is silver (Ag). The substrate is SiO₂/Si. The right side shows the schematic of the side view of the device representing thickness of each layer. The electrodes are both 50 nm thick and 25 nm of SiO₂ is sandwiched between them. (b) Illustrates the basic I-V characteristics of the Au/SiO₂/Ag volatile memristor. (c) Represents the fundamental mechanism of volatile switching. The *Set cycle* (HRS to LRS switching) is dominated by drift of Ag⁺ particles when high electric field is applied across the device. The Ag particles form a conductive filament across the electrodes and hence the resistance drops. As soon as the electric field drops below a certain threshold (*Reset cycle*), the filament starts rupturing (LRS to HRS switching) and forming discontinuous clusters to reduce its surface to volume ratio and this process is dominated by surface diffusion.

the dynamics of filament formation, we observed the switching behavior of our device under two different kinds of measurement protocols: (i) applying constant voltages and (ii) applying voltage at fixed sweep rates. All experiments were done at room temperature (300 K). The results from both types of experiments gave us great insight into various energy and time scales at which the switching occurs. In addition we also understood the threshold dynamics and mechanism of filament formation.

Under the application of constant voltage on the device, the time taken by the device to switch from its high resistance state (HRS) to low resistance state (LRS) was measured. This quantity is defined as switching time (t_{switch}). Fig 2(a) demonstrates a clear exponential decrease in the t_{switch} with increasing applied voltage (fit with adjusted $R^2 \approx 0.94$, meaning data agrees with the fit with 94% accuracy). This implied that the switching mechanism can be modeled as field driven thermally assisted ion conduction given by:

$$t_{switch} = \tau \exp\left(\frac{E_a - \beta qV}{k_B T}\right) \quad (1)$$

Here E_a represents the activation energy, β is the field enhancement factor, q is the charge of the electron, k_B is the Boltzman constant, T is the temperature, and τ is the attempt time. Activation energy is defined as the minimum energy required by an Ag^+ ion to hop and migrate within SiO_2 matrix.

The field enhancement factor, (β) as estimated from the slope of graph is equal to 0.21. $\beta < 1$ indicates that the filament formation is not completely field driven but also assisted thermally. The difference in the switching dynamics at different voltages depends on migration of Ag^+ ions within SiO_2 matrix at those voltages. The attempt time (τ) of Ag^+ ion migration at room temperature ranges in $10^{-11} - 10^{-9}$ s.

The intercept of the plot (Fig. 2(a)) was discovered to be 6.9, which indicates that the activation energy can be estimated to be 0.77 ± 0.12 eV. Application of electric field across the device terminals decreases this activation energy barrier by 0.21 eV/V at a constant temperature.

Such behavior also reveals another interesting property of memristors. When an I-V measurement is performed on a device by applying a voltage sweep, the observed V_{set} of the device is dependent on the sweep rate. This result is often overlooked and not reported in many research studies. We show in Fig. 2(b) that V_{set} of the device shows an exponential dependence on the voltage sweep rate of the measurement, meaning the faster the voltage sweep rate, the larger is V_{set} , in agreement with our filament formation model. Moreover, eq. 1 also suggests that V_{set} of the device should decrease linearly with increase in temperature (provided constant sweep rate), this has been verified and discussed in Fig.S2 of Supporting Information document. It should be noted that although I-V characterization of memristors seems to be a simple task from the viewpoint of the measuring technique, there are several aspects in the design of the experimental set-up and in the interpretation of data which need to be considered carefully.²⁶

In the next set of experiments, the resistive switching was observed by applying a voltage sweep to analyze the conduction mechanism of the device and the mechanism of filament formation. Fig. 2(c) shows the log-log plot of I vs V. This revealed several key aspects of filament formation. In the initial stages of the device when applied voltage is much smaller than the V_{set} , the device stays in HRS. However, under a certain voltage range, (highlighted in yellow arrows from 0.35 V to 0.78 V) we see an emergence of a metastable state where a stochastic current (conductance) stays in orders of nA (average of 22 nA over the range) and keeps fluctuating indicating the conductance, G , in order of $10^{-9}S$ which is $\ll G_0$ (quantum of conductance $G_0 = 77\mu S$). Thus the current represents the tunneling current flowing through the device. Beyond this metastable regime, when $V \approx V_{set}$, we observe that filament formation happens in two major steps: in the first step, $I \propto V^{1.9}$, which is an indication of trap-limited space charge limited current (SCLC), in the second step, $I \propto V^{10.8}$, indicating the trap-filled SCLC before the compliance current of $0.5 \mu A$ is reached.² This reveals significant information regarding formation dynamics of Ag CF.

Fig. 2(d) shows a schematic representation of several key stages of CF formation in the device. In the initial state of operation ($V \ll V_{set}$) the device remains in HRS state meaning there isn't enough energy supplied (E) to Ag^+ ions to hop into the SiO_2 matrix ($E < E_a$). With increase in voltage the effective energy barrier required by Ag^+ ions to hop is reduced, and hence the ion migration starts. The sudden increase in tunneling current of the device reveals that reduction of Ag^+ ions to Ag nanoparticles starts happening within SiO_2 matrix. The Ag particles get trapped within the defect sites of SiO_2 and start forming clusters. Several such disconnected clusters start assisting the tunneling current through SiO_2 matrix and hence the current shows a sudden increase from 10^{-10} A to 10^{-8} A. The reduction of Ag^+ ions within the SiO_2

indicates that rate of reduction (oxidation) is faster than the rate of Ag^+ ion mobility within amorphous SiO_2 . Further discussion on this intermediate conduction state will be presented in the next section. It should be noted that the voltage range of metastable regime is dependent on the sweep rate of measurement as discussed earlier. In this case, the sweep rate was 0.06 V/s. Eventually, due to increasing voltage, the size of clusters increases and the gap between them gets reduced resulting in a trap-limited SCLC conduction behaviour of the device ($I \propto V^2$). With the current rising as square of voltage, rapid joule heating of the clusters starts. This causes clusters to decrease their surface to volume ratio and hence they elongate in direction of electric field. This leads to stark increase in the electric field at the tip of the elongated clusters and therefore, the conduction starts increasing even more rapidly ($I \propto V^{11}$), till a complete and continuous filament is formed assisted by both electric field and joule heating. Finally the compliance current is reached. Thus by the help of two sets of experiments we could understand the entire mechanism and dynamics of filament formation.

It should be noted that we can clearly observe the asymmetric behavior of device in set half (voltage increasing) and reset half (voltage decreasing) of the cycle. Once a continuous filament is formed, the device can sustain I_{cc} for voltages much smaller than V_{set} as observed in reset half of the cycle. However, below a certain voltage $V = 0.14 V$ ($V \approx V_{reset}$) the current starts dropping but follows ohmic law ($V \propto I$), followed by events of sudden drops as the filament breaks. More details on CF relaxation will be discussed in the next section. The distribution of device to device variation in V_{SET} of 50 devices and cycle to cycle variation of a device for 50 cycles has been provided in Fig. S1 and S5 of Supporting Information.

Filament rupture dynamics

We will now proceed to analyze the filament rupture dynamics. Since Ag does not dissolve into SiO_2 , once the voltage is reduced or removed, the filament forms small clusters to minimize its Gibbs-Thomson energy at the interface between CF and the SiO_2 .²⁷ The rupture process is significantly fast and varies from milliseconds to nanoseconds in volatile memristors. Unfortunately, our measurement instrument couldn't record measurements at such a fast rate and hence we needed to adapt our experimental protocol in order to analyze the rupture phenomenon. For this purpose, we set the device in LRS by applying 2 V ($> V_{set}$) and after a time, t_0 we would drop the voltage to a very small read voltage ($V_{read} \ll V_{set}$) and measure the CF dynamics of the device as it transitions from LRS to HRS. Fig. 3(a) shows the measurement protocol. This type of study gave us crucial information regarding filament rupture mechanism.

Fig. 3(b) shows the observation of device as it transitions from LRS to HRS under the influence of various small read voltages V_{read} ranging from 0.1 V to 0.3 V. These results provide valuable insight into CF rupture dynamics. We observed that for very small V_{read} of 0.1 V and 0.15 V, the device transitions from LRS to HRS rapidly and the current falls from $I_{cc} = 0.5 \mu A$ to < 0.1 nA and then eventually decays to noise floor of the instrument (≈ 70 pA), whereas for $V_{read} \geq 0.2 V$ the device never completely returns to the HRS and stays in a metastable state between the LRS and HRS values for observation time of over > 120 s. The determination of conductance values ($G = \frac{I}{V}$) of the device at $V_{read} \geq 0.2 V$, reveals that the metastable state is achievable due to tunneling current flowing through the device assisted by Ag clusters trapped in SiO_2 matrix as discussed in previous section. Interestingly, closer observation into dynamics of device transition from LRS to HRS in case of $V_{read} = 0.1V, 0.15V$ discloses crucial insight (Fig. 3(c)). We observe that the transition from LRS to HRS happens in multiple steps (marked 1-4 in figure). Each step can be interpreted as a major filament rupture event where the filament disintegrates to smaller and smaller clusters. The inset of Fig. 3(c) shows that when the clusters get smaller, further splitting takes longer as the current decay takes longer. The schematic on the right most inset (Fig. 3(c)) shows a representative picture of current while the clusters are splitting. Analysis of the conductance values (G) at different V_{read} also gave us interesting insight into the filament rupture behavior. The ratio, $\frac{G}{G_0}$ is plotted against V_{read} in Fig. 3(d). We observe that device shows a sharp deviation from trap-assisted tunneling behavior near $V_{read} > 0.2 V$. This indicates that ($V \approx 0.2 V$) the size of cluster is large enough that isolated clusters can occasionally merge and form a larger cluster resulting in higher conduction current. A clear indication of isolated clusters merging and separating can be found in Fig. S6 of Supporting Information.

The mechanism of filament rupture is explained in a simplified schematic in Fig. 3(e). Initially, when the device is in LRS, the CF is continuous, but when the voltage is dropped to $V_{read} < 0.2 V$ the filament breaks down into numerous small clusters and hence the conductance decreases significantly. This also implies

Figure 2: **Filament formation dynamics.** (a) Shows the time taken by the device to switch from HRS to LRS when a constant voltage is applied to the device. The graph shows a linear relationship between the $\ln(t_{switch})$ v the applied V . The inset of the graph shows the V v t during the operation. The linear relation signifies a field driven thermally assisted filament formation mechanism. The mathematical relation of switching time (t_{switch}) and its dependence on various fundamental device parameters like activation energy (E_a), field enhancement factor (β), applied voltage (V), temperature (T) is also given. (b) The graph shows a linear relation between the observed V_{set} of a device vs the ($\log(V/s)$) of log of applied voltage sweep rate. (c) log-log plot of I vs V of the device. The sweep rate for this was 0.6 V/s. It was found that filament formation happens in multiple steps: at initial stage, we see a sudden increase (purple) in conduction followed by a stochastic metastable regime resulting from tunneling current assisted via trapped Ag nanoclusters. This is followed by trap-limited SCLC mechanism ($m \approx 2$) and at the later stage the process is dominated by trap-filled SCLC mechanism ($m \approx 11$). For $V = 0.14$ V ($V \approx V_{reset}$) an ohmic and electron tunneling conduction mechanism was observed ($m \approx 1$). It should be noted that we also observed a sudden drop in conduction (highlighted by pink arrow) which will be explained in the next section. (d) Represents a simplified schematic of different stages of filament formation. Initially at low electric field the injection of Ag ions in SiO_2 start, leading to very small tunneling currents. Then at higher voltages the Ag ions that get trapped in voids/defects of SiO_2 starts nucleating and there is an increase in conduction (trap-limited SCLC), this increased current leads to joule heating leading to increase in surface to volume ratio of Ag clusters and hence the local electric field at the tip of these clusters increases resulting in sudden increase in conduction current (trap-filled SCLC), finally the complete filament is formed which is quite thin and unstable at low electric fields $V < V_{reset}$.

that surface diffusion energy at these voltages is significantly more dominant than the electric field driven drift energy. However, when $V_{read} \approx 0.2$ V, the drift force starts competing with the surface diffusion and although the filament still disintegrates to Ag clusters, the cluster size is large enough to sustain a significant tunneling current. Therefore, we envisage that at surface diffusion energy is of the order of 0.2 eV. However, this value represents a lower bound (and a hypothesis), as the true thermal diffusion barrier is reduced by the applied electric field (Eq. 1). The surface diffusion energy barrier of Ag in oxide has been reported to be in the range of 0.5 eV -0.7 eV.²⁸ When the $V_{read} > 0.2$ V (0.77 eV > Energy > 0.2 eV), the cluster size increases further and now device can sustain even higher tunneling currents and reaches intermediate metastable states where its resistance, R is $LRS < R < HRS$.

In addition, the rupture dynamics also reveal that after every operational cycle, there is a probability of Ag nanoparticle accumulation within the SiO_2 matrix. This Ag accumulation in the dielectric has been reported by many studies, and over time ($> 10^3 \sim 10^4$ cycles), it causes the device to transition from a volatile to a non-volatile memristor (LRS state sustained). However, the device can be returned to its HRS state by a single negative voltage sweep, after which its volatility is restored and it resumes normal operation. The detailed endurance ($> 40,000$ cycles) of the device, and its transition from volatile to non-volatile memory and back, is depicted and discussed in Figs. S3–S4 of the Supporting Information.

Discussion

The present study elucidates the physics of threshold dynamics governing Ag filament formation and rupture in amorphous SiO₂-based memristors and demonstrates how metastable states arising from Ag nanocluster formation and their dynamics within the SiO₂ matrix can be exploited for reservoir computing, stochastic computing, and true-random-number generation. This intrinsic capability can be leveraged further to modulate the drift–diffusion interplay and shift the switching behaviour from abrupt (threshold/digital) to gradual (analog), modes beneficial for spiking and deep neural networks. Several recent device-engineering strategies illustrated how deliberate manipulation of this drift-diffusion interplay can be achieved through material stack design. Bousoulas et al.,²⁹ incorporated a VO_x layer into the Ag/SiO_2 stack to create a bilayer structure. Since the diffusion barrier of Ag filament is higher in VO_x , it suppresses the filament rupture mechanism and hence the device could maintain its LRS even at low compliance currents (1 μ A), which was not possible by unmodified Ag/SiO_2 stack. This demonstrates that increasing the diffusion barrier through materials choice can stabilize the filament against rupture and shift the device toward nonvolatile, analog behavior. A different approach was taken by Kang et al.,³⁰ instead of raising the diffusion barrier, they lower the cation mobility within the amorphous Si matrix by densification, and simultaneously enhance the in-medium reduction probability of Ag^+ by embedding Ti nanoclusters with a much lower reduction potential. This combination ensured that Ag^+ ions are reduced as discrete clusters within the dielectric rather than forming a single filament at the inert counter-electrode (Au) interface. The cluster-mediated conduction regime suppresses the positive feedback in the electric field (as discussed previously $I \propto V^{10.8}$) that normally drives abrupt switching. This work provided direct transmission-electron-microscopy evidence for in-medium cluster nucleation and confirms that the trap-assisted-tunnelling electrical signatures observed in the present study are the fingerprint of cluster-dominated conduction. Chaudhary et al.,³¹ used defect engineering in two-dimensional switching layers ($WSeO_x$ and WSe_2) to control the Ag diffusion pathways. By decreasing the defect density via plasma-assisted selenization, they confined the Ag transport to narrow, reproducible channels within the crystalline layer. This confinement dramatically reduced switching variability (SET/RESET voltage variation), stabilized the filament against stochastic rupture, and enabled deterministic nonvolatile operation with low device-to-device variation. The approach demonstrates that variability, arising from the atomic-scale stochasticity of diffusion through a disordered landscape, can be suppressed by structural ordering. Taken together, these complementary strategies—diffusion-barrier enhancement, in-medium redox probability control, and diffusion-pathway confinement, all address the same underlying drift–diffusion competition that governs filament dynamics. The present work provides the mechanistic foundation for these device-engineering approaches by quantifying the intrinsic activation energies and metastable intermediate states accessible in $Ag/SiO_2/Au$ stack.

Figure 3: **Filament rupture dynamics.** (a) Represents the measurement protocol to understand the filament rupture mechanism. A 60 s long 2 V voltage pulse was applied to device to keep it in LRS state for 60 s and then the voltage was dropped to a very small read voltage to observe the filament rupture dynamics. (b) Shows the device behavior at various small read voltages. The experiments give key insight to the filament rupture dynamics as we can observe at low read voltages (0.1 V, 0.15 V) the device current quickly falls to $\cong 0.1 - 0.09$ nA currents within a second and then decays to the noise floor of measurement instrument ($\cong 60$ pA), whereas for 0.2 V the current quickly falls and then stabilizes at $\cong 0.35$ nA for over 120 s. Similar long term stabilization of current was observed at 0.25 V and 0.3 V read voltages and a gradual increase in current with increasing V_{read} was also observed. Hence the device at these voltages represents a metastable state between HRS and LRS. (c) A detailed analysis of current decay at 0.1 V and 0.15 V reveals key insight in to the threshold dynamics of filament rupture. We observe that the actual filament rupture happens in 4 parts as resolved and illustrated (parts 1-4) in graph for 0.1 V case (blue plot). We see that the fall from $0.5\mu A$ to 0.09 nA happens in two jumps and then further current falls from 0.09 nA to 0.06 nA in two jumps (see right inset). Each jump signifies a major filament rupture event. In the schematic in the inset we show when a cluster is in process of further splitting, we observe a slow decay in current. (d) Demonstrate the relation between $\log(G/G_0)$ vs read voltage. The positive slope behavior indicates trap-assisted tunneling characteristics implying that current is tunneling through Ag clusters trapped inside the SiO_2 matrix. The sudden increase in conduction observed at the 0.21 V indicates that the cluster size is increasing because of merging of isolated clusters. The conductance current values at 0.1 V and 0.15 V were taken at $t = 65$ s. (e) Illustrates a simplified schematic of filament rupture mechanism, the filament formation and rupture is a constant competition between the electric field driven drift vs surface diffusion. When the read voltage is < 0.2 V, the surface diffusion energy is significantly more than drift force hence the filament ruptures to very small clusters and the device returns back to HRS. When the read voltage is > 0.2 V the drift energy is less than but comparable to diffusion energy and hence the filament breaks but doesn't totally disintegrate to small clusters and we observe larger tunneling currents.

Conclusions

We have established a comprehensive physical framework addressing fundamental questions about threshold CF formation and rupture behavior that governs the switching characteristics of the device and depicts the dynamic interplay between field driven drift and surface diffusion of Ag particles. Our systematic investigation revealed the formation of CF proceeds via field-activated thermally assisted ($E_a = 0.77 \pm 0.12$ eV, $\beta = 0.21$) drifting of the Ag^+ ions migrating from Ag terminal towards the Au terminal. The Ag^+ ions get trapped in the defect sites of dense and amorphous SiO_2 matrix and get reduced to Ag nanoclusters. These nanoclusters eventually grow and elongate due to joule heating and form a continuous filament. The CF rupture is governed by surface-diffusion dominated clustering of the continuous filament to minimize its Gibbs-Thomson energy. The presence of intermediate metastable conductance states sustained by trap-assisted tunneling current reveals that filament formation (nucleation process) starts within the amorphous SiO_2 and not from the Au electrode as expected from some simulations.^{32,33} This also reveals that the rate of redox reaction of Ag^+ in SiO_2 is much faster than rate of ion mobility. The existence of intermediate conductance levels and conductance fluctuations from probabilistic cluster dynamics, enables voltage controlled access to randomness essential for true random number generation in Internet of Things security applications and stochastic computing architectures. Observation of similar behavior at high speed pulse mode is a future aspect. Unlike pseudo-random number generators, the intrinsic atomic-scale stochasticity provides non-decryptable hardware-based randomness suitable for cryptographic applications.¹⁵⁻¹⁷

Our work not only brings key insight into the CF formation and rupture mechanism but also establishes design principles for implementing bio-inspired temporal computing in resistive switching devices, providing a foundation for next-generation adaptive computing architectures that capture the energy efficiency and cognitive capabilities of biological neural systems.

Associated Content Supporting Information

Statistical data for device-to-device and cycle-to-cycle variation; temperature-dependent V_{set} characterization; device endurance and life cycle data; trap-assisted tunnelling current observation.

Experimental Methods

The memristor devices used in this study were fabricated by standard optical photolithography followed by evaporation and liftoff (all three layers). The substrate used was p-type $\langle 100 \rangle$ Si with 300 nm of SiO_2 grown by wet thermal processing and was bought from Crystal GmbH. The patterned bottom electrode consisted of 50 nm of gold (Au) deposited by e-beam evaporator. A 2 nm adhesion layer of titanium (Ti) was deposited prior to Au deposition. 25 nm of patterned SiO_2 layer was deposited on top of Au electrode using RF sputtering in pure Ar environment of pressure of 10^{-3} mbar at 30° C. The final top electrode of silver (Ag) was patterned and deposited using e-beam evaporator. The thickness of Ag electrode was 50 nm. The images of the device were taken using Olympus DSX 1000 microscope. The devices were tested using Lakeshore Jannis ST-500 probe station at room temperature. A Keithley 4200 CS semiconductor parameter analyser was used for I-V measurements of the devices. The Au electrode was grounded for all measurements. All experiments were performed at room temperature of 300 K. About 50 devices were used to validate the results.

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Table of Content (TOC) Graphic

Mechanism of Volatile Resistive Switching

